

Results of Agricultural Reforms Being Implemented in the Khorezm Region

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Abstract: This article presents the results of reforms in agriculture of the Khorezm region according to the State program for the implementation of melioration measures and the financial resources spent. An analysis of changes in agriculture over previous years according to statistical data and the significance of the achieved results in the socio-economic development of the region is made. Proposals and recommendations for the development of agricultural production are developed.

Keywords: infrastructure activities, regional stability, infrastructure system, regional economy.

Introduction. In order to ensure macroeconomic stability and consistent economic growth in the Khorezm region, structural changes are being implemented in the economic sectors, with great attention being paid to further expanding entrepreneurial activity, developing the processing and service sectors, and attracting investments to the regional economy. As a result, sustainable growth is being achieved in all sectors of the socio-economic development of the region.

Reflecting the economic potential of the region are increasing year by year, indicating that the well-being of the population is improving. In recent years, the average growth rate of the gross regional product (GRP) in the region has been 106.5 percent, and in 2008-2014, the GRP growth rate was no less than 109.1 percent.

The main pillar of the regional economy is agriculture. Agriculture is developing steadily and has a constant growth trend, with an average growth rate of 105.1 percent, and the average growth rate for 2008-2014 was 106.8 percent [1].

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-3932 dated October 29, 2007 "On measures to radically improve the system of land reclamation" plays an important role in the sustainable and rapid development of agriculture. Also, the Resolution No. PP-1958 "On measures to further improve the land reclamation of irrigated lands and rational use of water resources in 2013-2017" adopted on April 19, 2013 is a logical continuation of the State Program for 2008-2012 [2, 3].

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, noted that as a result of the implementation of these programs, "since 2008, the reclamation condition of almost 1.5 million hectares of irrigated land in our country has improved, the area with high groundwater levels has decreased by 415 thousand hectares, or almost 10 percent, and the area with strong and moderate salinity has decreased by 113 thousand hectares" [4].

Reflection and discussion. Due to the low rainfall in the Khorezm region, agricultural work here is carried out only through irrigation. There are opportunities to produce abundant crops without reducing productivity by using water resources economically in agriculture.

In the region, land areas differ sharply by district according to their level of productivity. Average credit score of land by province 53, and lands with 91-100 points are almost non-existent. Lands with 81-90 points are present in Gurlan and Khiva districts, making up a small part of the total area. The most productive lands are located in Gurlan (55 points), and the least productive lands are located in Khazorasp district (47 points). In our opinion, the reason for the low fertility in Khazorasp district can be explained by the fact that the district is located close to the Tuyamoyin reservoir, which is the only one in the region and one of the largest reservoirs in our country, and that the groundwater is located closer to the land in this area than in other districts. The average fertility level in the remaining districts is almost the same and does not differ much. Most of the area of the region is made up of lands with average fertility.

This table shows that more than 90 percent of the region's soils are saline or susceptible to salinization. Before the implementation of the State Program for Improving the Reclamation Condition of Land, the average soil quality score was 53. In order to obtain high yields from agricultural crops, it is necessary to carry out reclamation measures to combat soil salinization [5].

In the Khorezm region, due to the weak natural flow of groundwater, in cases where the conditions of artificial drainage systems, i.e. collector-drainage systems, are unsatisfactory, vertical water exchange in these areas is strong and leads to salinization of groundwater and soil cover. Therefore, the use of these lands in agricultural production requires the constant implementation of a system of land reclamation measures, primarily measures aimed at reducing salt leaching and groundwater [6].

Analysis and results. Within the framework of the State Program for Improving the Reclamation Condition of Irrigated Lands for 2008-2014, 238 projects were implemented in the Khorezm region, the total cost of which amounted to 160.8 billion soums. Of these, 164 projects were implemented to carry out repair and restoration work on reclamation facilities, the cost of which amounted to 64.9 billion soums. 74 projects were implemented to construct and reconstruct reclamation facilities, the cost of which amounted to 77.9 billion soums. Also, capital expenditures in the amount of 17.9 billion soums were made to purchase reclamation equipment.

The Khorezm region, reconstruction and construction of collector-drainage networks with a length of 314 km, as well as repair and restoration works on collector-drainage networks with a length of 8773.7 km, were carried out. At the same time, current and capital repairs were carried out at 87 pumping stations. As a result, the land reclamation condition of 175.3 thousand hectares of arable land improved. This, in turn, serves to increase the productivity of agricultural crops. During 2008-2014, the volume of agricultural production increased by almost 3 times, that is, from 721 billion soums to 2236.8 billion soums. At the same time, the volume of gross product produced in the sector increased from 237.3 thousand tons to 258.2 thousand tons in cotton cultivation, and its productivity increased from 23.6 centners/ha to 25.9 centners/ha. The volume of grain production increased from 180.9 thousand tons to 445.7 thousand tons. Of these, wheat production increased from 143.7 thousand tons to 223.4 thousand tons, and rice production from 30.4 thousand tons to 121.0 thousand tons. We can also see that the production of potatoes, melons and vegetables from winter crops has also increased significantly. In particular, potato production during these years increased from 11.8 thousand tons to 108.4 thousand tons, vegetable production from 105.8 thousand tons to 501.8 thousand tons, and melon products from 36.5 thousand tons to 125.6 thousand tons. The production of fresh fruits and grapes increased from 52.1 and 8.1 thousand tons to 161.4 and 36.8 thousand tons, respectively.

These achievements and milestones are the result of implemented reclamation activities. As an example, we can see changes in the productivity of agricultural crops.

As gradual reform of the agricultural sector, optimization of farm lands - correct distribution of economic opportunities, reduction of expenses per hectare of land area and production of more agricultural products, maintenance of soil fertility and regular, advanced agrotechnical measures are considered important. As a result, by rationally using land, water, material, technical and

labor resources, socio-economic efficiency and profitability of the farm will be increased, and the financial and economic condition of farmers will improve.

Most importantly, reforms in the agricultural sector have radically changed the attitude of farmers to land and property. Now, farms are not limited to grain and cotton growing, but have the opportunity to increase their income and provide employment to the population of the region by establishing sectors such as fishing, poultry, livestock, beekeeping, production, processing, trade and services. In particular, as of January 1, 2010, 10,276 farms were operating in the Khorezm region, with a total land area of 242.3 thousand hectares. During these years, the land of farms has been optimized. As a result, the rationalization of arable land of farms in accordance with the procedure established by law allows optimizing the income of farms. Between 2009 and 2014, the number of farms decreased to 5,568, while the combined land area increased to 252,000 hectares.

Farms operating in agriculture, 48.2 percent, are engaged in cotton and grain growing. Farms operating in the field of horticulture and viticulture account for 23.4 percent, livestock farms for 10.8 percent, fisheries for 6.2 percent, vegetable and melon farms for 1.5 percent, and farms producing other agricultural products account for 10 percent.

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 362 dated December 15, 2015 “On measures to optimize the areas of land plots allocated for the management of farms” sets out a plan of measures aimed at further increasing the efficiency of farm activities, as well as ensuring the rational use of land and water resources, strengthening the financial and economic situation of farms, and a number of tasks, including optimizing the arable land of farms. As a result of the implementation of the tasks set out in this resolution, it is planned that the number of farms in the Khorezm region will reach 6,049.

Nowadays, farms are being transformed into diversified farms, and agricultural production is being diversified, and all types of crops are being grown on farms. This indicates that this is the result of the modernization processes of agricultural enterprises. In the process of modernization, technical and technological re-equipment of the agricultural sector, problems are emerging that need to be resolved. In particular, there is almost no or low level of cooperative cooperation between producers.

In our opinion, it is advisable to develop various mechanisms that encourage farmers to take initiative. In this regard, improving the land reclamation condition should not be carried out only within the framework of the State Program, but also by agricultural producers, interested farms (farms, peasant farms, shirkat farms, agricultural cooperatives, specialized farms, SIUs, etc.) of their own free will (at the expense of internal financial resources) to implement a plan of measures aimed at expanding economic activities and increasing profits. The desire for innovation (innovative qualities) of management personnel is somewhat lacking. Because increasing profits is the main goal of economic entities.

Conclusions and suggestions. Based on the analysis we have carried out above, as a result of the reforms carried out in the agricultural sector, the land reclamation condition of about 175 thousand hectares of land in the region has improved. The productivity of agricultural crops has increased, and the volume of gross domestic product production is also growing every year. The population's demand for food products is being satisfied, and export opportunities are increasing.

To further develop the economic potential of the Khorezm region, deepen reforms in the agricultural sector, implement modernization work in the sector quickly and efficiently, and take additional measures to eliminate some emerging problems and shortcomings.

We propose to implement the following tasks in order to increase the effectiveness of work aimed at further developing agriculture:

- Together with the Committee for Coordination of the Development of Science and Technology under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Farmers' Council of

Uzbekistan and other interested organizations, develop a strategy for the development of farms based on the experience (standards) of foreign countries;

- in the optimization of agricultural land, determination of crop areas taking into account the types of crops and the possibility of selling them at free market prices (maximizing profit);
- to increase the obligation of insurance organizations in the implementation of beneficial agreements on cooperation in the development of agricultural production;
- improving the mechanisms of using financial resources of water management organizations, including water consumers' associations, as well as their material and moral incentives at the expense of internal resources, in the implementation of works aimed at improving land reclamation;
- for farmers and peasant farms to exchange practical skills in efficient land use with the examples of the most advanced farms;
- expanding the scope of practical work to improve the skills of agricultural workers, as well as to develop their skills in using new innovative equipment and technologies;
- of investments in agriculture and water management at the level of individual regions and develop new plans and proposals to increase their importance for the republic (regularly);
- store agricultural products and fully satisfy the population's demand for food products throughout the year;
- organize the export of agricultural products through terminals to neighboring countries or other countries and expand business activities.

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